

Bordering without men: an ethnography of daily life of Hawraman women

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Abstract

The opportunities and challenges of borderlands are intricately tied to women, far more than meets the eye. Border studies traditionally focus on male actors, often neglecting the experiences of women residing in border regions. Hawraman, a borderland similar to other regions in Kurdistan, has faced both opportunities and challenges. In recent years, men from Iranian Hawraman have migrated to Iraqi Kurdistan as "migrant border laborers," working on a daily-wage basis away from their families. This study employs ethnography, grounded in the concept of *intersectionality*, to delve into the everyday lifeworlds of Hawrami border women. Our findings suggest that academic circles and urban populations must gain a deeper awareness of the diverse lives led by border women and prioritize their perspectives on social change. This requires engaging with their lived experiences, including their definitions of femininity, identity, discrimination, and everyday struggles. These women often endure much of the year without male family members, shouldering life's burdens alone. The ethnographic findings indicate that addressing the daily struggles of women in Hawraman involves confronting systemic barriers that hinder empowerment—not just for women, but for men as well. Thus, alleviating specific forms of discrimination against women cannot be achieved in isolation, as these challenges are deeply intertwined with systemic injustices faced by men.

Keywords: Hawraman women, Border studies, Intersectionality, Migrant labor, Kurdish women, Kurdistan, Iran

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Author's Note:

*This article is a revised English version of a Persian-language article previously published in the *Journal of Iranian Social Studies* (2024, 17[4]:29–51). The original Persian version is accessible via the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22034/jss.2024.2022425.1826>.*

This version has been prepared for international dissemination and open-access availability. A separate DOI will be assigned upon upload to a public repository.

Original article received: 07 February 2024 | Published: 22 October 2024.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary life of border inhabitants, the concept of the border is a slippery signifier, perpetually relegating individuals to the margins. This aligns with Simmel's notion of the "marginal person" (1950:413), described as a "hybrid being" who inhabits the space between distinct and sometimes antagonistic cultures. This liminal figure belongs simultaneously to both cultures and to neither. One of the most prevalent understandings of borders relates to political and geographic demarcations. The phenomenon of borders was constructed differently with the emergence of modern nation-states. Before their formation, "frontiers" delineated the territories of empires, whereas modern states, driven by nationalist ideologies, established precise borders as symbols of cultural and political sovereignty. Consequently, borders have become vital to the "everyday life" of contemporary human beings. Border regions in Iran, due to their cultural and linguistic commonalities with communities across borders, often face a condition of "otherness." From the perspective of central regions, borderlands are often perceived as "alien" or "outsiders" (see Mary Douglas, 1966). Douglas argues that anything deviating from the "normal" or dominant status becomes marginalized, imbued with taboo qualities that provoke anxiety and disrupt one's sense of stability (Fakouhi, 2013:263). Events such as birth, death, or pregnancy—moments that deviate from the continuum of daily routine often carry taboo qualities. Similarly, the condition of living at the border can be analyzed as an "abnormal" phenomenon that contributes to the marginalization of border dwellers. For central regions, borders remain latent threats to their "normal" position of dominance. Yet, borders have evolved beyond mere geographic locations; for the border inhabitant, these spaces are imbued with symbolic meanings that entangle them in the modern human experience. Geertz (1998:47) emphasizes that "interpreting the symbolic dimensions of social actions—whether in art, religion, science, or law—does not evade the existential contradictions of human life. Instead, it delves into these complexities". Modern anthropological theories, from the 19th century to today, grapple with how macro-level theories often fail to address the micro-level dynamics of lived human experiences. Geertz posits that the cultural concept he endorses is essentially a semiotic one, stating that humans are creatures suspended in webs of meaning they themselves have spun. Cultural analysis, therefore, is not an experimental science seeking laws, but an interpretative endeavor aimed at uncovering meaning (Geertz, 1998:9–10). Geertz's interpretive approach to culture, blending Heideggerian hermeneutics and Gadamer's fusion of horizons, alongside an ethnographic focus on the field and its agents, offers an expansive lens for examining phenomena. This perspective aligns with Fredrik Barth's (1969) focus on the agency of actors in constructing distinctions, as discussed in *Ethnic Groups and Boundaries*. These frameworks offer insightful tools to understand borderland phenomena, irrespective of gender. This study's central question investigates the everyday lifeworlds of Hawrami border women, analyzing how they experience and navigate their roles within these contexts.

Background of the Study

The people of Hawraman, as residents of a borderland, have increasingly integrated the concept of the border into their lives over the past century. Modernization processes over recent decades have

profoundly altered their lifeworlds, particularly for women. Alongside emerging opportunities, many challenges have also surfaced, akin to other regions worldwide. Structural transformations in social and economic domains, as McLaren (2017) argues, have brought about significant shifts [Ghaderzadeh et al., 2024]. However, the "border" in Hawraman renders these transformations distinctive. One of the most prominent aspects of this transformation involves the migration of male family members to engage in labor across borders. These men, who might be fathers, husbands, or sons, are often compelled to work as migrant border laborers. Their absence leaves women to take on dual, often conflicting roles within the household. Such dual-role responsibilities place immense strain on border women, who navigate spatial (border) and temporal (daily life) constraints that compound their marginalization in intersectional ways. The concept of intersectionality elucidates how multiple factors interact to exacerbate discrimination and inequality. Border women not only contend with the specific marginalizations associated with living in a border region but also experience the compounded dynamics of "being a woman." These intertwined factors perpetuate suppression and discrimination. While border-related research has proliferated, the specific experiences of border women—particularly their dual-role negotiations—remain underexplored. Discussions of border women often implicitly seek to "rescue" them. Yet, as Abu-Lughod (2013:127) cautions, efforts to "save" women from phenomena like "honor killings" can obscure the deeper cultural violence at play. Thus, without viewing border women as active agents with complex dual roles, analytical efforts risk inadequacy. Investigating how Hawraman women experience this phenomenon, therefore, becomes a critical and nuanced question.

Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative approach to examine the everyday lifeworlds of Hawrami border women through ethnography [Irandoost et al., 2023]. This ethnographic inquiry aligns with interpretive anthropology, primarily associated with Clifford Geertz, as articulated by Riviere (Fakouhi, 2014:218). This methodology entails a contextually grounded exploration of the phenomenon. While it shares similarities with phenomenology in capturing lived experiences, it does not limit itself to commonalities, also encompassing differences. The fieldwork involved direct observation and participation, with an additional layer of interpretative analysis to reflect on the dual perspectives inherent to ethnographic studies [Babasafari, 2020]. The research field comprises three villages—Taa, Farsabad, and Farajabad—located in the district of Muchesh in Gavrud rural sub-district within the Hawraman-Javrud region of Kurdistan Province. Most residents are orchardists, cultivating fruits such as quince, walnuts, and strawberries. Historically, the villages of Farajabad and Farsabad were part of Taa, but challenges in commuting to and from the orchards led some families to settle near their farms, resulting in the establishment of new villages. Culturally, these villages exhibit a high degree of homogeneity compared to other areas of Hawraman. The Hawraman region lies along the mountainous western borders of Iran and eastern Kurdistan (Iraq). Its boundaries extend north to the villages of Soran in Sarvabad and Sanandaj Counties, west to Soran in Iraqi Kurdistan, south to the villages of Paveh and Kamyaran Counties, and east to parts of Kamyaran and Sanandaj Counties (Mahmoudi, 2015). Political geography has often defined the region,

overshadowing the linguistic and cultural commonalities of its inhabitants. Portions of the so-called Hawraman region in Kermanshah Province, for instance, are not ethnically Hawrami but are included within the administrative boundaries of Kermanshah's Hawraman. This study delineates its research field not by contemporary political borders but by employing Bahman Soltani's classification in *The History of Hawraman*. Soltani divides the region into three parts: Hawraman Takht, Javrud, and Lahun (Soltani, 2007:356).

Research Findings

The Concept of "Being a Woman"

We visited a site called "Vahretav," meaning "sun," a part of the orchards in Taa village. Unlike other orchards further from the village, such as Sham or Nesar, the proximity of Vahretav allows women to spend significant time there. In contrast to the shaded orchards of Nesar, sunlight floods Vahretav throughout the day. The trees in Vahretav stand orderly, with no broken branches or weeds in sight. The strawberry plants are meticulously pruned, evoking the care of a skilled hairdresser. Women gather here daily, cultivating the land and hosting informal social gatherings. We joined one such gathering and soon met Minoo, a visitor from Sanandaj. Despite her presence in this rural environment, Minoo had not assumed the roles typically required of local women whose husbands work as border laborers. Her experience resembled that of a researcher observing laborers in a brick kiln—detached and noncommittal. Through the lens of Pierre Bourdieu's concept of participant observation, Minoo could not fully comprehend the lived realities of the women in Vahretav. Her understanding of femininity differed fundamentally from theirs. For women like Zhina, a widow who raised four children by working in the orchards, femininity is intertwined with hardship and resilience [Ahmadi et al., 2022]. Zhina remarked:

When my husband passed away, I became like a piece of driftwood in a river. Life was never easy before, but his death ended me. I put on a pair of men's trousers and told myself, 'Zhina, you were a woman, but now you must be a man.' Every time my son says he wants to work in Iraqi Kurdistan, it feels like I'm breaking into pieces. I died when my husband passed away, and now I keep dying a little more each day.

For women like Zhina, being a woman is not a static state but a precarious negotiation of identity. Their lives hover between presence and absence, oscillating between being integral to the community and marginalized by systemic invisibilities.

The Construction of Borders

Borders are neither static nor universally understood. Political events and cultural shifts redefine their meaning for locals and external observers alike. Economic, social, and cultural lives in border regions undergo rapid changes with each new treaty, conflict, or geopolitical maneuver. Maryam, a

resident of Taa, whose financial circumstances afford her more leisure and social engagement, shared her perspective on the awareness required by border residents:

Once, one of my husband's friends from Isfahan visited us. He told me, 'I didn't expect your people, despite your lack of formal education, to be so aware of history, politics, and current affairs.' I replied, 'We have to be, sir. We must always prove ourselves because we differ in language, ethnicity, and religion. Or we must stay informed about what policies are being planned for us, as no place is as uncertain as ours.'

Historically, the residents of Taa, Farsabad, and Farajabad did not perceive themselves as border dwellers, given their geographic distance from the physical border. However, the contemporary construction of "borderness" through symbolic and political narratives has increasingly defined their identity [Fayaz et al., 2019]. This phenomenon aligns with Heidegger's concepts of temporality and spatiality, as explored in his analyses of the "everydayness" of Dasein. Such interpretations are palpable in the research field, where the repetitive rhythms of daily life reinforce border identities. Daily life becomes the primary site for producing meaning, as posited by both structuralist and post-structuralist theories.

The Taboo of the Border

The border itself has become a "taboo" for the inhabitants of these regions, transforming border dwellers into "the other"—outsiders in their own homeland. The border disrupts the "continuous order of the everyday," a concept Mary Douglas (1966) describes as essential for maintaining stability and alleviating anxiety. This disruption manifests as a persistent reminder of marginalization and fragility for border residents. Although we, as researchers, are native to this region, the behavior of locals toward outsiders reveals the profound ambiguity of "the other." The people of these villages exhibit remarkable hospitality, treating strangers as if they were born there. This makes it challenging to apply Margaret Mead and Gregory Bateson's notion of "distance" between the observer and the observed. Instead, everything appears intimately "close" in their interactions, erasing the boundaries that might typically delineate "us" and "them." Yet, the construction of "the other" is not absent in these areas. It emerges subtly, depending on how an outsider positions themselves in relation to the community. A stranger emphasizing differences becomes an "other," while one who highlights commonalities is accepted as "one of us." This relational approach to identity construction underscores the cultural significance of borders in shaping perceptions of self and otherness. In recent decades, mass media and globalization have redefined the symbolic meanings of borders, eroding their taboo status in some ways while reinforcing them in others. The symbolic power of borders, deeply entrenched and abstract, remains resilient. However, the collective experiences of Kurdish communities, shaped by historical transitions, suggest a preference for fluid and multiplicitous identities. As Kurdish nationalism grows, the taboos surrounding political borders evolve, yet new boundaries—both literal and symbolic—continue to be constructed. Minoo, a kindergarten teacher and sociology graduate from Taa, observed:

If someone here once identified as fully Iranian, they risked being accused of siding with the regime by their fellow Kurds. On the other hand, denying such identification might make them appear separatist to non-Kurdish Iranians. Personally, I felt stuck in limbo for years because borders seemed so determinative. Now, my brothers are mostly living abroad, and I, too, might leave someday. Many people like me have resolved this dilemma by adopting cosmopolitan identities or simply ceasing to care about these rigid definitions.

Chiyman, another resident, shared a personal story about her daughter, who joined the Kurdish Freedom Party (PAK) in Iraqi Kurdistan:

At first, whenever I encountered anyone, I thought they were talking about my daughter. I was sure they pitied me, thinking, 'How can she hold her head high after her daughter fled?' But now, I think, what's the difference if she moves to another city within these borders or across them? She's still among people who share our language and culture. Public attitudes have also changed over the years. Borders no longer hold the same weight they used to.

The Missionary Complex of “Saving” Women

The socio-economic conditions of Farsabad differ significantly from those of Farajabad. The newer homes and improved amenities in Farsabad reflect its residents' relatively better financial standing. This disparity also extends to the lives of women. While Farajabad women often work to contribute to their families' survival, women in Farsabad typically seek financial independence or engage in economic activities out of choice. For instance, as autumn transitions into winter, Farajabad women spend months cracking walnuts to support their families. Meanwhile, some women from Farsabad also perform this task, but they do so sporadically and under far less financial pressure. In Farajabad, this work is often tied to debt and economic struggle. During a field visit, we encountered a group of women cracking walnuts. Among them was Ronak, a Farsabad woman adorned with gold jewelry. Confident and articulate, she shared her philosophy:

A woman must be self-sufficient. Why should I rely on a man for a single penny? I bought all this gold myself. If I can provide for myself, what need do I have for a man?

In response, her sister-in-law from Farajabad replied:

Ronak, you're speaking from privilege. Mashallah, you're well-off, but what about us? We borrow money to survive. Do you think my husband, if he were a border porter, would tolerate me spending money on jewelry instead of contributing to the household? People would gossip, saying, 'She's no real woman, letting her husband carry heavy loads while she flaunts gold.'

This exchange highlights the futility of imposing a universal solution on women's issues, even within neighboring villages. Such discrepancies raise critical questions about the efficacy of a missionary-like approach to "saving" women in these contexts. As Lila Abu-Lughod argues, feminist perspectives often fail to detach themselves from Enlightenment ideas of progress and modernity, preventing a deep anthropological understanding of women's lives in non-elite settings (Fakouhi, 2019:96). This

sentiment resonates deeply with the challenges of studying Hawraman, where external perspectives frequently romanticize or vilify the lives of local women. In these villages, women shoulder visible and invisible burdens. Their resilience is a testament to their agency, yet their struggles are inseparably linked to those of the men in their lives. Women cannot be "saved" in isolation; addressing their issues requires addressing the systemic challenges that entangle the entire community.

Discussion and Conclusion

Marcel Mauss's concept of the total social fact suggests that every social phenomenon contains traces of religious, legal, moral, and economic dimensions. Similarly, the phenomenon of "the border" and "border life" in Hawraman operates within a web of interconnected influences. To isolate specific factors as primary causes would be reductive. In Hawraman, the lives of women and men are intertwined in ways that make it impractical to separate their challenges. Women's issues are deeply enmeshed with the socio-economic struggles faced by their fathers, husbands, and sons. Without recognizing these overlapping layers of discrimination, proposed solutions risk ineffectiveness. The findings of this study reveal that many women in Hawraman carry the weight of family life in the absence of male family members, exacerbated by the taboos surrounding both borders and femininity. However, this does not mean that men enjoy better conditions. On the contrary, the systemic pressures on both genders amplify family-wide challenges. In such circumstances, framing women solely as victims to be "rescued" is counterproductive. Addressing the issues faced by Hawraman women requires acknowledging their roles as active agents and considering the broader socio-cultural context. As border taboos shift and new gender dynamics emerge, the concept of "womanhood" in these regions will likely transform. Ultimately, the problems faced by women in Hawraman cannot be resolved without addressing the systemic inequalities affecting men. Yet, the unique "otherness" of women in these contexts demands additional attention. "Womanhood" here is an interactive construct—one deeply shaped by the broader socio-political realities of the border, yet distinct in its gendered experience of marginalization.

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